

Cinemagraph: Effectiveness in Delivering Content Through Moving Image

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ABSTRACT

Moving elements is a part of interactive approaches that attracts our view to discover more. Different approaches result in a variety of results in delivering information, for example still image is used for poster campaigns and video is used for television commercial ads. Currently, still image and motion image (video) are the major media widely used especially in social media like in Instagram and Facebook. Cinemagraph technique is a new photography technique that combines two media which is video and still image to become a moving image, used to attract viewers at their first impressions. This study is focusing on the introduction of cinemagraph technique to be part of the new approaches especially in social media together with the other two media choices. Purpose of this study is to determine the effectiveness of these three media in delivering the content and see how far viewers react through the content presented. Results from this study are expected to help in gaining data to enhance the next future research, specialized in content study and the technique itself. As for the conclusions, this study only discusses on the surface since the main objective is to introduce the technique and identify the effectiveness of the media.

Keywords: *Cinemagraph, Interactive, Moving Element, Media Approach, Moving Image*

INTRODUCTION

New media is one of the communications approaches that reveals different ways with different impact. For instance, still image is uniquely advertised as poster while motion image or video directly used to advertise on television and social media platforms. Photography or still image has undoubtedly become more intimate – the smartphone as a permanent attachment to the self – and social media platforms have become increasingly networked and interwoven into daily routines, making photography a component of

nearly everything. Photograph or still image is one of useful media to be part of the communication ways, but the content only focuses on still with the use of colors and elements in it that are related to photography. Images, technologies, and practices associated with photography have seen significant transformations since the turn of the twenty-first century, as have the prevalence, significance, and cultural worth of the visual (Pasternak, 2021). Additionally, video technology allows for a wide range of 'natural' contexts, such as workplaces, informal conversation, and educational interactions, to be examined in greater depth. It shows the real situations of what is happening on the scene to make it more impact with the motion image moves in a certain period. Although these two approaches have become major options for all major platforms, somehow the type of content is different according to the media choice, for example health campaigns on these two media will result in different feedback on viewers, some perhaps get more influence by the still image while others on the video. On the other hand, technique in photography has evolved and varies to be chosen, and one of it is cinemagraph, which is a new technique famous from the movie *Harry Potter* where it shows the scene of Hogwarts magical notebook moving without any characters on it. Cinemagraphs are a popular new type of visual media that lie in-between photos and video; some parts of the frame are animated and loop seamlessly, while other parts of the frame remain completely still (Bai et. al., 2013). It believes that this technique will be the next new media to deliver effective messages in an interactive way towards the audience. Cinemagraph, with its aspects supporting and shaping visual design of aesthetics, as a result of increasing number of mobile devices representing an efficient and innovative visual design of mass communication, will undergo changes and developments including production, distribution, presentation and content (Erol, 2016).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Nowadays, people are moving towards the technology and new trends in lifestyle and everyday life, from cooking to driving based on the era from previous traditional methods to the latest robotics and interactive contents available at the tip of fingers thru a variety of platforms. The so-called new media technologies – often referred to as Web 2.0 – encompass a wide variety of web-related communication technologies, such as blogs, wikis, online social networking, virtual worlds, and other social media forms. These trends tend to make life easier by introducing the latest technology in every sector and industry, for example the social media platform creates an easy lifestyle of getting any information only through one platform from doing learning something to creating anything with only watching the media advertised. One of the most important advantages of the use of social media is the online sharing of knowledge and information among the different groups of people (Baruah, 2012). The dissemination of information in a digital format also contributes to a growth in people's communication abilities, particularly those of learners and students at educational institutions. Because of the proliferation of online tools and technology, not only has communication been facilitated in an infinite number of different ways, but the very methods in which we communicate, as well as the ways in which we discuss and think about communication, are also changing. The nature of our social life, both on an interpersonal and a communal level, may undergo significant changes as a result of the advent of social media.

New Media Approaches (social media)

Generally, the media landscape is undergoing rapid transformation. The borders between media types are getting more blurred, and in many situations, they are even merging. There is a shift in the way people consume media, and fundamental changes in the circumstances under which media is produced, at the same time There is a growing worldwide sector that creates a wide range of media material. For the first time in human history, media have become a major part of our daily lives and are now one of the greatest worldwide companies. The current media revolution may be studied from a variety of perspectives, including technological, economic, and social and humanistic. New relationships between

the medium and the user contradict the old idea of a one-way mass media. Even while conventional mass media are still dominant, there are more and more options for interactive services and personalized consumption. There is also the possibility for huge, worldwide organizations to have more control over production and distribution via these new technology capabilities. Companies on the global (and regional) scale must now decide which media channels to employ for their message, and they must also remain abreast of what is being published about them in both conventional and new media, to make informed decisions about their public relations strategies. Arola (2007) explained about the term of new media as 'media in transition' to show the transition of period changes from old media to new media according to the era phase. Clearly, new media may be characterized using a variety of different approaches (Friedman, 2017) and each of the approaches may give different results and impact to the viewers. To be specific, from the total number of current human population of 7.7 billion, at least 3.5 billion of these numbers are online, which proves that one-in-three people in the world were on social media (Patel, 2019). According to the statistics, 54% of internet users were spending time watching shows and films on streaming services while 43% were using social media.

Cinemagraph Technique

It is one of the newest techniques available instead of still image and video, cinemagraph is a file that consists of 2 types of technique which is photo and video into one file and highlights the movement parts to become a moving image. Cinemagraph is a new medium that combines the benefits of static images and videos; most of the frame is static, but some parts animate in a seamless loop (Bai et. al., 2013) for example the portrait of kids playing kite on the field, showing the kite's tail moving around but the rest of the photo is in still condition, making the whole image look alive. The term "cinemagraph" refers to an image that successfully combines motion and stillness in a manner that is not only visually appealing but also simple to comprehend, simple to remember, and visually captivating. It is a photograph with a living moment inside it (Burg, 2014). The interactive moving elements makes the cinemagraph looks appealing more than other media, for example still image only serve static subject while motion image shows multiple shots that turns out to be video, serving more seconds of attention and requires viewers to spend more time to see the message, even though it is clearly the best option to deliver content. In a cinemagraph, the attention of the consumer is not distracted by motion; rather motion builds up the interest and retention levels (Khan, 2016). In spite of the fact that the majority of the picture is static, the illusion of a live frame may be achieved by subtly moving one or more items in the foreground or the background in a repetitive fashion.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, a quantitative method has been done to identify the effectiveness of cinemagraph technique through participants through online surveys. Researchers constructed one online survey by using google form, consisting of 30 variables and seven sections. Each of the sections consists of around 6 to 7 variables on average, and 3 of the sections are directly focused on the topic discussed. The total of 198 respondents were involved, most of them aged between 19 till 21 years lived mostly around Putrajaya, and Kuala Lumpur. The questionnaire was handled through online, and one media of cinemagraph technique was previewed as a supporting element in several parts of the questionnaire. Meanwhile, the session was held around 10 minutes for the questionnaire to be answered by the respondents. After the session, the data collected has been done with descriptive analysis by showing the averages and standard deviations of numerical data, as well as the frequencies and percentages of categorical data.

FINDINGS

Figure 1. The cinemagraph technique
 (Source: Author's personal collection)

Table 1. Variables for the survey questionnaire and the result

No.	Variables	Results
1	I know what the cinemagraph technique is.	Strongly agree – 8.6% Agree – 33%
2	I do know that cinemagraph technique is a combination of photo and video in one file.	Strongly agree – 12.1% Agree – 42.9%
3	I can clearly see the cinemagraph technique in the Public Service Announcement (PSA) campaign shown.	Strongly agree – 11.6% Agree – 40.4%
4	I can see the movement element in the picture shown above.	Strongly agree – 15.2% Agree – 50.8%
5	After I see the picture shown, I can see the information received and want to know more about this issue	Strongly agree – 12.2% Agree – 53.8%
6	After I see the picture shown, I do get any information from the topic shown above	Strongly agree – 10.1% Agree – 49.5%
7	From the picture shown, I can understand clearly the cinemagraph technique	Strongly agree – 14.7% Agree – 51.3%

8	From the picture shown above, I clearly can see the moving parts / moving element	Strongly agree – 15.7% Agree – 59.9%
9	From the first impression, I clearly can see the interactivity in the picture shown above	Strongly agree – 11.1% Agree – 60.6%
10	I would like to see more of this campaign with cinemagraph technique	Strongly agree – 15.7% Agree – 46.2%
11	I would love to see more of this moving technique feature in future advertising	Strongly agree – 15.9% Agree – 38.2%

Data analysis reported all the results from the questionnaire held. With the total of 198 respondents involved, all the data were extracted successfully. Figure 1 shows the example of cinemagraph technique to clarify the technique itself and to help some of the questionnaire section related with this technique. In the table 1 above, showed the results from the data analysis and only eleven variables that strongly related with the objective of this study has been focused on. First variables measure how far the respondent is familiar with the cinemagraph technique, and 33% of them used to see this technique. Next variable measured the detail of the cinemagraph technique which consists of 2 files, still image and video, and 42.9% knew about this technique combination. From this, it is clearly shown that this technique is brand new and still not reach the full familiarity among the viewers. Cinemagraph approach offers a new visual language that was never explored before (Witabora & Homan, 2019). Moving to the next variable, respondents been showed the media of cinemagraph on public service announcement (PSA) with cinemagraph technique as supporting document, and 40.4% agreed that they can see the technique clearly with a touch of PSA concept in it which bring to the next variable on element movement in the media showed, half from the respondent agreed they clearly see the movement element in the media showed. From this, it stated that these variables were more focusing on the movement element in the technique, to attract the first impression of the viewers. While most of the image is still, a subtle, repeated movement of one or more objects in the foreground or the background creates an illusion of a living frame (Khan, 2016). Following this, next variable measured how far the respondents received the information through the technique in PSA and 53.8% agreed they clearly notice the message delivered to them and are eager to know more about it. In addition, after showing the supporting media of cinemagraph technique to the respondents, 59.9% agreed can see clearly the moving parts of the PSA while 60.6% admitted enjoyed the interactive element in the first impression of the technique, because cinemagraphs are able to creatively and successfully bring attention to a certain topic because they freeze the majority of the moving components in the image and animate just a select number of them, if any at all. Another point is, the last two (2) variables were more focusing on respondents' opinion and thoughts on seeing more of the cinemagraph technique in future, and 84.4% from the total of both variables agreed to the variables.

CONCLUSION

As for the conclusion, the objective of this study is to see the effectiveness of moving images of cinemagraph works in delivering content with interactive elements. While much of the new data derived from this study, researchers are focusing only on the surface to see how far this technique can perform as new media. Fortunately, according to the result respondents gave positive feedback on the technique because this concept of new media is still new and some of the respondents were unfamiliar with this moving image, and it is new to them to be discovered. This technique of cinemagraph is believed to be a

new technique option in any digital platform instead of still image and video, on the other hand video and still image have their own capabilities and advantages to compare with cinemagraph. But with what the technique can offer, researchers believe it will be the next big thing in the creative industry. In short, future research would be done especially focusing on detail and in depth such as the moving element, platform media available, and option available for cinemagraph technique can be used for. Plus, with social media platforms being seen to be a major trend nowadays, cinemagraph techniques have a bright future ahead to be well developed.

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REFERENCES

- Bai, J., Agarwala, A., Agrawala, M., & Ramamoorthi, R. (2013). Automatic cinemagraph portraits. *Computer Graphics Forum*, 32(4), 17–25. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cgf.12147>
- Witabora, J., & Homan, D. K. (2019). The use of cinemagraph effect in the creation of digital illustration work: A review. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1175(1). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1175/1/012247>
- Erol, E. (2016). *Evaluating of the Cinemagraph Technique in Context of Motion in Photography*. 9840.
- Pasternak, G. (2021). Photographic Digital Heritage in Cultural Conflicts: A Critical Introduction. *Photography and Culture*, 14(3), 253–268. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17514517.2021.1953763>
- Friedman, L. W., & Friedman, H. H. (2011). The New Media Technologies: Overview and Research Framework. *SSRN Electronic Journal*, April. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1116771>
- Baruah, T. D. (2012). Effectiveness of Social Media as a tool of communication and its potential for technology enabled connections: A micro-level study. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 2(5), 1–10. <https://doi.org/ISSN 2250-3153>
- Arola, K. L. (2007) *New Media, 1740–1915*. Edited by Lisa Gitelman and Geoffrey B. Pingree. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 2003. 271 pp, Technical Communication Quarterly, 16:4, 480-483, DOI: 10.1080/10572250701372821
- Friedman, L. W. (2017). *High Impact Areas of the New Media Technologies : A Review THE NEW MEDIA TECHNOLOGIES : OVERVIEW AND RESEARCH FRAMEWORK* Linda Weiser Friedman Professor , Department of Statistics & Computer Information Systems Baruch College and the Graduate Center of the. November.
- Patel, L. (2010). The rise of social media. *T and D*, 64(7), 60–61. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315563312-21>
- Burg, B. A. (2014). *Cinemagraphs*. Retrieved October 12 , 2016, from <http://nonsensesibility.com/>: <http://nonsensesibility.com/blog/2012/03/cinemagraphs-beck-and-burg/>
- Khan, F. B. (2016). Cinemagraph: A Fusion of Still Images and Motion Video for Science Communication in a New Media Convergent Ecosystem. *Journal of Scientific Temper (JST)*.